

Final conference

ImProDiReT

*Improving Disaster
risk
Reduction in
Transcarpathian
region*

*GeoRisk assessment
of Solotvyno
Methodology, results
and application*

*IGS NASU Results presented by
Prof. Stella Shekhunova*

Shayan, 2020 – 01 – 30

Солотвино в 1980-1990 роках

The increasing complexity of mining conditions (catastrophic water inflows into the mines) and catastrophic collapses led to mines flooding and the allergic hospital underground departments shutdown.

Підземні відділення алергологічної лікарні

Підземна лабораторія
Інститут фізики НАН України

The increasing complexity of mining conditions (catastrophic water inflows into the mines) and catastrophic collapses led to mines flooding and the allergic hospital underground departments shutdown.

This, in turn, caused social tension, firstly due to job losses in mines, and then due to the unsystematic development of recreational resources, redistribution of access to them, arrangement of a regional waste deposit within the village territory, uncertain development potential, and hazardous processes manifestations.

Solotvyno mines, 2014

BUILDING A SAFER TOMORROW WITH LESS RISKS FOR THE COMMUNITY

The ImProDiRet Project mission is to develop a coordinated community-driven Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) action plan aimed at protecting and building resilience of the Transcarpathian people, their environment, property and cultural heritage. The project seeks to attain three primary results.

[CONTINUE READING →](#)

One of the aim of the project was an **assessment of the hazards and risks of natural and natural-technogenic exogenous geological processes** that affect or limit the development of Solotvyno

Features of the Solotvyno historical past, its geographical position and geological structure of the territory define Solotvyno as a

- historical (CMU resolution of July 26, 2001 №878),
- resort and recreation center (Transcarpathian..., 2011)
- and as a territory subjected to a hazardous environmental situation of anthropogenic nature at the state level as a result of a catastrophic termination of mining operations (expert resolution by the MES of Ukraine 09.12.2010 №02-17292/165).

These aspects have influenced the definition of the methodology for hazards risk assessment, which are of natural and antropogenic character.

Hillfort from 2-1 BC

Hazard (sometimes threat) - a process, phenomenon or human activity that may cause loss of life, injury or other health impacts, property damage, social and economic disruption or environmental degradation

Hazards may be natural, anthropogenic or socio-natural in origin.

***Natural hazards** are predominantly associated with natural processes and phenomena.*

***Anthropogenic hazards**, or human-induced hazards, are induced entirely or predominantly by human activities and choices. This term does not include the occurrence or risk of armed conflicts and other situations of social instability or tension which are subject to international humanitarian law and national legislation.*

*Several hazards are **technogenic-natural or socio-natural**, in that they are associated with a combination of natural and anthropogenic factors, including environmental degradation and climate change.*

Research Stages of Hazards Identification for Solotvyno

HAZARDS

identification & hazards list compiling
characterization
mapping
analysing & ranking
territory zonation on hazards manifestation probability

Vulnerability identification & assessment
Exposure identification & assessment
Vulnerability and exposure mapping

RISK ASSESSMENT AND MAPPING
RISK ANALYSIS

Список небезпек

- Карст та суффозія
- Схилова ерозія та зсуви
- Повені, паводки та підтоплення
- Селі
- Сильні снігопади
- Зливи
- Сильна ожеледь
- Засуха
- Хімічна, пожежна та вибухонебезпека

LIST OF HAZARDS

- **Karst and suffosion**
- **Slope erosion and landslide**
- **Seasonal floods and flash floods and flooding**
- Mudflow
- Heavy snowfalls
- Heavy rains
- Drought
- Black ice
- Chemical Hazard, Fire and Explosion Risk

★ **Karst and suffosion (subsidence, karst and karst-suffusion sinkholes, collapses)**

The territory of karst manifestations is relevant to the shallow occurrence of the salt dom roof

★ **Karst** is the geological process, which arise from the dissolution with underground or surface water, of soluble rocks such as limestone, dolomite, and gypsum or rock salt (Solotvyno case). As a result, negative landforms form on the Earth's surface and various cavities in the rock mass

Karst hazards involve fast-acting processes, both on the surface and underground (e.g., collapse, subsidence, slope movements, and floods) and their effects (e.g., sinkholes, degraded aquifers, and land surface), which threatens the people lives, property loss, and impedes the construction, operation of buildings and engineering facilities

Mine No8 western flank

★ Flood and flooding map for Solotvyno

Floods (seasonal floods and flash floods) – hazardous hydrological phenomena – a significant flood of the area due to water levels rising in a river or other reservoir caused by heavy rainfall, snow melting, wind gusts of water, dams destruction etc.

Floods on mountain rivers, such as Tisza in Solotvyno, are forming very quickly, which puts high demands on the promptness of forecasting and alerting the population.

Flood risks in Solotvyno are projected within the Tisza River floodplain. (Figures 1-4: Zones 14-16).

Particular attention should be paid to the protection of water intake and treatment plants located in seasonal floods and flash floods areas.

Flood and flooding during seasonal floods and flash floods :

- 1 – flood and flooding area (Tisza river) заплава р.Тиса;
- 2 – flooding area/підтоплення;
- 3 – flooding area (high level of ground water around streams);
- 4 – probable flooding area (after drainage system collapse);
- 5 – lakes of different genesis (natural and technogenic);
- 6 – rivers and streams;
- 7 – horizontal lines (though 5 m);
- 8 – roads and highway H09;
- 9 – railway;
- 10 – Solotvyno contour and state border zone.

Flood and flooding (inventory) hazards map for Solotvyno

Flooding. The most intensive flooding processes occur in the areas adjacent to the of rivers floodplains, sites in areas influence of reservoirs, canals or mine fields, etc.

Flooding within the building areas, where the permanent disturbance of the natural regime, moistening and raising the level of groundwater are record, leads to a significant deterioration of the population living conditions, the functioning of economic facilities and contributes to emergencies.

Flood and flooding during seasonal floods and flash floods:

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Flooding / підтоплення

Zone 4: areas of drainage systems influence

Subsidence, flooding

Portal of the drainage "Tisza gallery" on the Tisza River
An approximate water drainage from the drainage tunnel "Tisza-gallery" is $1.24 * 10^6 \text{ m}^3 / \text{year}$ (40 l / s or 3400 m³ / day)

Water discharge on the slope of the Tisza-gallery / Tisa-shtolnya

★ Slope erosion and landslides

First floodplain terrace:
slope erosion, landslides, soil flow

★ **Slope processes** - cause the destruction of a slope by moving loose material or blocks of rocks / soil down the slope under the influence of gravity.
These include landslides, debris flow, rock falls etc.

Підрізка дестабілізація схилів, поверхнева ерозія

The acceleration of these processes can be caused by: wetting of soil with rainfall, snowmelt, earthquakes, slope erosion and ill-considered human activity (slope cutting, blasting and earthworks, deforestation etc.).

The activation of the landslides depends in particular on the intensity of the slope moisturizing by ground- and surface water.

Drainage ditch along the foot of the northern inland dam slope

Examples of landslide and flooding deformations of the slope due to the irregular diversion of surface runoff to the drainage ditch (deformed tree trunks and tree cutting)

Violation of internal stability of the northern slope of the dam at the device of individual sewerage systems

An example of the equilibrium profile violation of the northern internal slope of the dam and its spontaneous building

INVENTORY MAP OF HAZARDOUS TECHNOGENIC-GEOLOGICAL AND ENGINEERING-GEOLOGICAL PROCESSES

Legend. Zones of hazardous processes manifestations (1-16): 1 – catastrophic (a) and undefined degree (b): karst-suffosion sinkholes, subsidence, collapses, landslide formation, erosion etc. (the area of mine fields of shafts No. 7, 8, 9 and Black Mochar); 2 – potentially dangerous: subsidence, karst-suffosion sinkholes, surface displacement, micro-landslides, erosion etc. (anthropogenically and technogenically disturbed territory of ancient mining activities); 3 – moderate: rock salt dissolution, formation of lakes of different salinity and surface deformation; 4 – moderate: slope erosion and suffosion, enhanced by anthropogenic activity on the dam main body; 5 – moderate: flooding, waterlogging, leaching (Zaton area); 6 – moderate: slope erosion, technogenic flooding etc. (southwestern slope of the 1-st Tisza River floodplain terrace); 7 – moderate: slope erosion, ravine formation due to inherited tectonic disturbances, technogenic flooding, etc. (western part of the Tisa River 1-st and 2-nd floodplain terraces slopes); 8 – insignificant: slope erosion, paleolandslides, etc. (Mahura mount slope); 9 – insignificant: slope erosion, paleolandslides, flooding etc. (1-st and 2-nd Tisza River floodplain terrace southeastern slope); 10 – moderate: potential technogenic flooding after Tisza drainage gallery collapse; 11 – insignificant: manifestations of suffosion in tectonic disturbances influence area, technogenic flooding etc. (mine No. 9 western flank); 12 – insignificant: slope erosion, periodical technogenic flooding (Mahura mount); 13 – insignificant: manifestations of flooding; 14 – insignificant: hydrocarbon contamination (southern (a) and northern (b) part of the abandoned underground infrastructure facility); 15 – potentially dangerous, moderate: floods and flooding with various degree of reliability (probability) 3 %, 50 %, 75 % respectively; 16 – without visually established hazardous processes manifestations; 17 – potentially dangerous, moderate manifestations: flooding of different genesis; 18 – basic data as to hazardous exogenous geological processes manifestation areas (absolute elevations, surface slope, area of manifestation); 19 – lakes and waterlogged lands of different genesis (natural and technogenic/anthropogenic); 20 – rivers and streams; 21 – horizontals (though 5 m) and hypsometric data; 22 – sinkholes and collapses outlines; 23 – streets with buildings, roads, highway H09 (a), railway (b); 24 – Solotvyno contour (a) and the state border zone (b); 25 – contours of mines (approximative); 26 – contours of mines (according to detailed engineering schemes, combined); 27 – main drainage galleries.

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RISKS ASSESSMENT AND MAPPING
RISK ANALYSIS

Quantitative evaluation of hazardous processes manifestations

- 1 – manifestations number, units/area (number of karst sinkholes, paleolandslides, deformation development areas, subsidence, flooding within estimated area);
- 2 – manifestations area, km² (summarized / average manifestations area within estimated area);
- 3 – spatial susceptibility of territory (the percentage of summarized hazardous processes manifestations area within estimated area);
- 4 – activity (the percentage of active forms to summarized manifestations number);
- 5 – temporal dynamics of development (years of activation, characterized by a significant increase in the number / area / degree of manifestations, for the period 1919-2019).

Subsidence and landslide risks for the AOI

Risk Level	Attributed class
Below 0.75	LOW
In the range [0.75 2]	MODERATE
In the range [2 3]	HIGH

Surface Subsidence Map for Solotvyno

Зона видобутку та експлуатації надр

Зони провалів

Шахти

Забудова

Житова та цивільна

Комерційна, громадська та приватна

Виробнича

Церкви

Транспортні

Площі просідання

деформація мм/рік

1.25

0

-3

-6

-9

-12

-15

-18

-21

-24

0 0.15 0.3 0.6 0.9 1.2 км

1:25 000

- Solotvyno dome structure
- Solotvyno mine generalized
- Solotvyno galleries
- Solotvyno lakes
- Probability of danger gzhimprom shp
- accidental
- is possible
- often
- remote
- Tissa
- Roads
- Relief line
- Solotvyno

- | | | | | | | | |
|---|----|----|----|----|----|----|----|
| 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 | 8 |
| 9 | 10 | 11 | 12 | 13 | 14 | 15 | 16 |

Zonation of the hazardous technogenic-geological and engineering-geological processes manifestations for the Solotvyno territory

Legend. Zones of hazardous processes manifestations (1-16): 1 – catastrophic (a) and undefined degree (b): karst-suffusion sinkholes, subsidence, collapses, landslide formation, erosion etc. (the area of mine fields of shafts No. 7, 8, 9 and Black Mochar); 2 – potentially dangerous: subsidence, karst-suffusion sinkholes, surface displacement, micro-landslides, erosion etc. (anthropogenically and technogenically disturbed territory of historical mining activities); 3 – moderate: rock salt dissolution, formation of lakes of different salinity and surface deformation; 4 – moderate: slope erosion and suffusion, enhanced by anthropogenic activity on the dam main body; 5 – moderate: flooding, waterlogging, leaching (Zaton area); 6 – moderate: slope erosion, technogenic flooding etc. (southwestern slope of the 1-st Tisza River floodplain terrace); 7 – moderate: slope erosion, ravine formation due to inherited tectonic disturbances, technogenic flooding etc. (western part of the Tisa River 1-st and 2-nd floodplain terraces slopes); 8 – insignificant: slope erosion, paleolandslides, etc. (Mahura mount slope); 9 – insignificant: slope erosion, paleolandslides, flooding etc. (1-st and 2-nd Tisza River floodplain terrace southeastern slope); 10 – moderate: potential technogenic flooding after Tisza drainage gallery collapse; 11 – insignificant: manifestations of suffusion in tectonic disturbances influence area, technogenic flooding etc. (mine No. 9 western flank); 12 – insignificant: slope erosion, periodical technogenic flooding (Mahura mount); 13 – insignificant: manifestations of flooding; 14 – insignificant: hydrocarbon contamination (southern (a) and northern (b) part of the abandoned underground infrastructure facility); 15 – potentially dangerous, moderate: floods and flooding with various degree of reliability (probability) 3 %, 50 %, 75 % respectively; 16 – without visually established hazardous processes manifestations; 17 – potentially dangerous, moderate manifestations: flooding of different genesis; 18 – figures in circle reliability* of hazardous technogenic-geological and engineering-geological processes manifestations, %; 19 – lakes and waterlogged lands of different genesis (natural and technogenic/anthropogenic); 20 – rivers and streams; 21 – horizontals (though 5 m) and hypsometric data; 22 – sinkholes and collapses outlines; 23 – streets with buildings, roads, highway H09 (a), railway (b); 24 – Solotvyno contour (a) and the state border zone (b); 25 – contours of mines (approximative); 26 – contours of mines (according to detailed engineering schemes, combined); 27 – main drainage galleries.

*Assessment shown in k ...% – reliability (provision percentage) is the probability of such a combination of factors equal to k% (0.0k). 1% reliability/provision is a probability, a combination of factors causing the rise of river water level (equal to 0.01). It can also be interpreted as: 1% reliability/provision – 1 time in 100 years; 2% reliability/provision – 2 times per 100 years; 4% reliability/provision – 4 times per 100 years.

ImPro iret

0 250 500 M

1. **LAW OF UKRAINE CODE OF CIVIL PROTECTION OF UKRAINE (Verkhovna Rada Gazette, 2013, No. 34-35, p.458) revision as of November 28, 2019, base – 263-IX; 01.01.2020, base – 294-IX.**
2. **Law of Ukraine “On the National Target Program of Protecting the Public and Territories from Man-Made and Natural Emergencies for 2013 – 2017” Date of entry into force: January 1, 2013 (actual)**
3. RESOLUTION OF THE CABINET OF MINISTERS OF UKRAINE from February 15, 2002 No. 175 “On Approval of the Methodology for Assessment of Losses from the Consequences of Emergency Situations of Technogenic and Natural Character”, (As amended according to CM N862 (862-2003-p) of 04.06.2003) Kyiv
4. RESOLUTION OF THE CABINET OF MINISTERS OF UKRAINE of July 15, 1998 No. 1099 “On the Procedure of Emergency Situations Classification” (Regulation repealed under KM N 368 (368-2004-p) of 24.03.2004), Kyiv
5. STATE BUILDING REGULATIONS OF UKRAINE "Planning and Building of Territories" (SBR V.2.2-12: 2019), Kyiv, Ministry of Regional Development, Construction and Housing and Communal Services of Ukraine, 2019, 185 p.
6. NATIONAL STANDARD OF UKRAINE “Guidelines on engineering protection of territories, building and construction from flooding and flood” (NSTU-G B V.1.1-38:2016) SE “UkrNDNC” Ukrainian Research and Training Center of Standardization, Certification and Quality, Kyiv, 2016, 141 p.
7. NATIONAL STANDARD OF UKRAINE “Guidelines for engineering protection of territories, buildings and structure” (NSTU-G B V.1.1-37:2016) SE “UkrNDNC” Ukrainian Research and Training Center of Standardization, Certification and Quality, Kyiv, 2016, 94 p.
8. State Building Regulations of Ukraine “Engineering protection of territories, buildings and structures from landslides and avalanches” (SBR V.1.1-46: 2017) Main principles, Ministry of Regional Development, Construction and Housing and Communal Services of Ukraine, Kyiv, 2017, 41 p.

У законі України визначення ключового поняття «ризик» приводиться у його європейському розумінні, на відміну від раніше прийнятого у законодавстві, зокрема й Законі «Про об'єкти підвищеної небезпеки», а саме:

«ризик – кількісна міра небезпеки, що визначається функцією двох змінних – імовірності небажаної події й розміру збитку від неї».

Для цілей розрахунків вважають:

$$R = P \times U,$$

де змінна P – це ймовірність аварії (небажаної події), а U – розмір її наслідків (збиток).

Законодавчо у нашій країні значення прийнятного ризику не встановлені.

Ми використовували рівні, рекомендовані світовими товариствами ВООЗ й МООП:

незначний ризик – $R \leq 1 \cdot 10^{-6}$;

припустимий ризик – $1 \cdot 10^{-6} \leq R \leq 5 \cdot 10^{-5}$;

високий (терпимий) ризик – $5 \cdot 10^{-5} \leq R \leq 5 \cdot 10^{-4}$;

!!! неприпустимий ризик – $R \geq 5 \cdot 10^{-4}$.

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The hazard relationship for multi-hazard probability assessment

Geological hazard	Flooding	Landslides	Subsidence	Karst
Flooding	—	Coupled	Coupled	Coupled
Landslides	Chain	—	Independent	Independent
Subsidence	Caused by	Chain	—	Coupled
Karst	Caused by	Independent	Coupled	

ts – soil type, litology,
 m - thickness,
 α - slope angle,
 hw – groundwater level,
 kt – technogenic trigger

Technogenic / antropogenic activity is taken into account as the summarized / total coefficient of hazardous processes manifestations activation / stabilization:

0,1-1,0 - the stabilizing effect of protective systems and constructions availability / presence (water-control dam, New Tisza-gallery, Tisza-gallery);

1.1-2.0 - activating effect from mining and building activities.

Specific land use for the Solotvyno territory

Legend. Zones of hazardous processes manifestations (1-16): 1 – catastrophic (a) and undefined degree (b): karst-suffusion sinkholes, subsidence, collapses, landslide formation, erosion etc. (the area of mine fields of shafts No. 7, 8, 9 and Black Mochar); 2 – potentially dangerous: subsidence, karst-suffusion sinkholes, surface displacement, micro-landslides, erosion etc. (anthropogenically and technogenically disturbed territory of historical mining activities); 3 – moderate: rock salt dissolution, formation of lakes of different salinity and surface deformation; 4 – moderate: slope erosion and suffusion, enhanced by anthropogenic activity on the dam main body; 5 – moderate: flooding, waterlogging, leaching (Zaton area); 6 – moderate: slope erosion, technogenic flooding etc. (southwestern slope of the 1-st Tisza River floodplain terrace); 7 – moderate: slope erosion, ravine formation due to inherited tectonic disturbances, technogenic flooding etc. (western part of the Tisa River 1-st and 2-nd floodplain terraces slopes); 8 – insignificant: slope erosion, paleolandslides, etc. (Mahura mount slope); 9 – insignificant: slope erosion, paleolandslides, flooding etc. (1-st and 2-nd Tisza River floodplain terrace southeastern slope); 10 – moderate: potential technogenic flooding after Tisza drainage gallery collapse; 11 – insignificant: manifestations of suffusion in tectonic disturbances influence area, technogenic flooding etc. (mine No. 9 western flank); 12 – insignificant: slope erosion, periodical technogenic flooding (Mahura mount); 13 – insignificant: manifestations of flooding; 14 – insignificant: hydrocarbon contamination (southern (a) and northern (b) part of the abandoned underground infrastructure facility); 15 – potentially dangerous, moderate: floods and flooding with various degree of reliability (probability) 3 %, 50 %, 75 % respectively; 16 – without visually established hazardous processes manifestations; 17 – flooding of different genesis; 18 – lakes and waterlogged lands of different genesis (natural and technogenic/anthropogenic); 19 – rivers and streams; 20 – horizontals (though 5 m) and hypsometric data; 21 – sinkholes and collapses outlines; 22 – streets with buildings, roads, highway H09 (a), railway (b); 23 – Solotvyno contour (a) and the state border zone (b); 24 – contours of mines (approximative); 25 – contours of mines (according to detailed engineering schemes, combined); 26 – main drainage galleries. Zones of social and business activity (27-29): 27 – public and business, 28 – educational (a), medical (b), cultural and sports (c); 29 – landscape-recreational (recreation and tourism); residential areas (30-33): 30 – manor / farm, 31 – blocked low-rised; 32 – mixed multi-unit; 33 – gardening societies (country houses); 34 – zone of enterprises and communal and warehouse facilities; 35 – zone of transport infrastructure (railways); 36 – zone of engineering infrastructure (electricity, gas, water supply and wastewater remove); 37 – existing cemeteries (objects of the 3-rd class of sanitary classification) (a), cultic buildings (churches) (b), a memorial zone (closed cemeteries) (c); 38 – a special zone of Ministry of Interior (State Border Service, State Emergency Service).

Category of land for the Solotvyno territory (according to StateGeoCadaastre data)

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Загальна оцінка території населеного пункту
(фондові/літературні та польові дослідження)

Природний блок, карти

Техногенний блок (карти)

Карта зонування н.п. небезпечних ГР

Техногенні тригерні фактори

Вразливість E, V

- Шахтні виробки
- Підземні дренажні виробки
- Об'єкти критичної інфраструктури
- Щільність забудови
- Населення

Визначення ймовірнісних характеристик розвитку небезпечних геологічних процесів

simple multiple

Карта-схема імовірності виникнення небезпечних ГР

Населення

Об'єкти критичної інфраструктури

Житлових споруд

Забруднення довкілля

$P(H)$

E, V, D

РОЗРАХУНОК РИЗИКІВ

- Індивідуальний
- Соціальний
- Економічний
- Екологічний

Приведення результатів до інтегральної бальної оцінки ризику небезпечних ГР для населеного пункту

КАРТА-СХЕМА ІНТЕГРАЛЬНОГО РИЗИКУ $R(H)$

TOTAL RISK ASSESSMENT FORMULA

$$R(H) = \{P, E, V, D\}$$

TYPES AND MATHEMATICAL MODELS OF NATURAL AND TECHNOGENIC RISK

Risk Type	Character	Formula	Units	Risk Ranking	
Individual	Injure or death people from the population group	$R_i(H) = P(H) \cdot V_s(H)$	persons/of persons · year	Insignificant	$< 2.7 \cdot 10^{-7}$
				Small	$(2.7 - 3.3) \cdot 10^{-7}$
				Middle	$3.3 \cdot 10^{-7} - 10^{-6}$
				Large	$10^{-6} - 10^{-5}$
				Very large	$10^{-5} - 10^{-4}$
				Extremely large	$> 10^{-4}$
Economic	Destruction or damage of the territories and objects of economy	$R_e(H) = P(H) \cdot E_e \cdot V_e$	thousand UAH / m ² · year	Insignificant	$< 2 \cdot 10^{-4}$
				Small	$(2 - 10) \cdot 10^{-4}$
				Middle	$(10 - 20) \cdot 10^{-4}$
				Large	$20 \cdot 10^{-4} - 10^{-2}$
				Very large	$(1 - 2) \cdot 10^{-2}$
				Extremely large	$> 2 \cdot 10^{-2}$

ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL RISKS OF 5-STOUREY BUILDING DAMAGE (OBJECT LEVEL)

$$R_b(H) = P(H) \cdot E_S(H) \cdot V_b(H) \cdot D_b$$

$P(H)$ – вірогідність прояву карстових провалів у часі (100 років) $0,973 \text{ пр/км}^2 \cdot \text{рік}$

$E_S(H)$ – вірогідність (геометрична) ураження будинку карстовим провалом у просторі

$$E_S(H) = \frac{S_b}{S_z} = \frac{867,1 \cdot 10^{-6}}{2,85} = 304,25 \cdot 10^{-6}$$

S_b – площа будинку; S_z – площа всієї зони $2,85 \text{ км}^2$ *probability of karst collapses*

$V_e(H)$ – уразливість – вірогідність (економічна) ураження будинку карстовим для першого випадку $0,35$, для другого – $0,65$.

D_b – вартість будівлі до ураження $22 \times 10^3 \text{ грн./м}^2 \times 867,1 \text{ м}^2 = 19,08 \text{ млн. грн.}$

$$R_{b1}(H) = 0,973 \cdot 304,25 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot 0,35 \cdot 19,08 \cdot 10^6 = 1976,9 \text{ грн./рік}$$

$$R'_{b1}(H) = \frac{1976,9 \text{ грн./рік}}{867,1 \text{ м}^2} = 22,8 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ тис. грн./м}^2 \cdot \text{рік}$$

за **50 років становить 0,98 % вартості будівлі**

Індивідуальний ризик для проживаючих у будинку людей при утворенні карстових провалів:

$$R_i(H) = P(H) \cdot V_S(H)$$

$V_S(H)$ – соціальна уразливість

$$V_S(H) = V_e(H) \cdot V_{St}(H) \cdot V_{SS}(H)$$

$$V_{S1}(H) = 0,35 \cdot 0,42 \cdot 0,0041 = 0,0006027 \quad V_{S2}(H) = 0,65 \cdot 0,42 \cdot 0,63 = 0,172$$

$$V_{St}(H) - \text{соціальна уразливість людей у будівлі у часі} \quad V_{St}(H) = \frac{11,8 \cdot 311,45}{24 \cdot 365} = 0,42$$

$$R_{i1}(H) = 0,973 \cdot 0,0006027 = 5,86 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ люд./люд.} \cdot \text{рік}$$

$$R_{i2}(H) = 1 \cdot 0,172 = 0,17 \text{ люд./люд.} \cdot \text{рік} = 17 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ люд./люд.} \cdot \text{рік}$$

more than the background level in Ukraine $0,067 \cdot 10^{-4}$

SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF ENVIRONMENTAL RISK ESTIMATION SOLOTVYNO (LOCAL LEVEL)

Flood

Sum: 202075556,74 UAH

Flooding

Sum: 111375690,79 UAH

Karst and slope processes

Sum: 40096296,46 UAH

SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF ECONOMIC RISK ESTIMATION FOR SOLOTVYNO (LOCAL LEVEL)

Multi-hazard assessment

(karst, slope processes, flood, flooding, subsidence), building, oki (+railway, roads, land)

Differentiated economic risk

- for building

Sum: 5800262,71 UAN

- for critical infrastructure

Sum: 353547544,01 UAH

Risk Map of Natural and Natural-Antropogenic Hazards for Solotvyno

Legend. Risk of natural and natural-antropogenic hazards (1-3): 1 – karst processes: catastrophic (a), high (б), medium (B), low (r); 2 – slope erosion: high (a), medium (б), low (B); 3 – seasonal and flash floods: high (a), medium (b), low (c); 4 – lakes and waterlogged lands of different genesis (natural and technogenic / anthropogenic); 5 – rivers and streams; 6 – horizontals (though 5 m) and hypsometric data; 7 – sinkholes, collapses and weakened zones outlines; 8 – streets with buildings, roads, highway H09 (a), railway (b); 9 – Solotvyno contour (a) and the state border zone (b); 10 – contours of mines (approximative); 11 – contours of mines (according to detailed engineering schemes, combined); 12 – main drainage galleries.

Руйнування житлового будинку внаслідок карстових процесів в Солотвино (фото 10.07.2013)

Карстові воронки на території Солотвинського солерудника (фото 10.07.2013)

Area of subsidence and collapses (mine 8)

Zones 1, 2:

The most dangerous is the zone 1 of catastrophic manifestations within the salt dome eastern part. It is characterized by a constant intensive course of karst-suffosion processes, accompanied by the formation of numerous sinkholes and deformations, complicated by irregular local subsidence, salinization, flooding, waterlogging, slope erosion and soil erosion, with a significant unpredictable threat of their negative manifestations.

It includes the area of mine fields of shafts No. 7, 8, 9 and Black Mochar territory. Additionally, it's characterized by the rock salt body deconsolidation with loss of load-bearing strength, significant degradation of the landscape, indefinitely long course of hazardous karst-suffusion natural and antropogenic processes; differs both by significant revitalization complexity and any involvement in economic activity; requires constant instrumental monitoring. Given the significant deep technogenic disturbance of the rock salt body, the lack of information and the complexity of technogenic and geological processes, it is surrounded by a zone of uncertain probability degree of the natural and antropogenic hazardous processes manifestations (zone 2).

Ділянка осідання на північний захід від Чорного Мочару

Максимальна швидкість осідання -27 мм/рік
(за даниними Космічного агенства України)

Розширення Чорного Мочару

«Live» Black Mochar slope

Zone	Zone	Hazards	Hazards characterization	Probability, %	Consequences / Impact		Risk Assessment Integrated
					Kind of Impact	Severity	
1 2 (1)	<i>Area of mine fields of shafts No. 7, 8, 9 and Black Mochar</i>	Karst (collapse-type & surface-type) suffusion, flooding etc.	collapses, sinkholes, subsidence, landslides	100	Human loses and injures	5	Catastrophic
					Economic losses	5	
					Environmental impact	4	
3 (2)	<i>Anthropogenically and technogenically disturbed territory of historical mining activities</i>	Karst, suffusion, erosion, micro-landslides, etc.	sinkholes, surface displacement, subsidence, landslides	50	Human loses and injures	4	High
					Economic losses	4	
					Environmental impact	3	
4 (3)	<i>Northern lakes in Zaton area</i>	Karst (surface-type)	formation of lakes of different salinity, surface deformation	40	Human injures	3	Medium
					Economic impact	3	
					Environmental impact	2	
6 (5)	<i>Southwestern part of Zaton area</i>	Karst (surface-type), flooding	waterlogging, leaching	25	Environmental impact	3	low

SEVERITY	CONSEQUENCES			PROBABILITY, %				
	People	Assets	Environment	< 1	1-10	11 - 49	50 - 90	> 90
1	Slight injury or health effect	Slight damage	Slight effect					
2	Minor injury or health effect	Minor damage	Major effect					
3	Major injury or health effect	Moderate damage	Moderate effect					
4	PTD or up to 3 fatalities	Major damage	Major effect					
5	More than 3 fatalities	Massive damage	Massive effect					

Risk Calculation

Zone 1

Individual risk, person / year:

$$R = 2,12 * 10^{-3};$$

Individual risk for residential houses, house / year:

$$R = 4 * 10^{-3};$$

Risk for residential houses economic losses, UAH / year:

$$R = 264 * 10^3;$$

Individual risk for critical infrastructure objects, object / year :

$$R = 19,125 * 10^{-3};$$

Risk for land property, unit / year: $R = 46,9$

Zone 2

Individual risk, person /year: $R = 9,1 * 10^{-3}$

Zone	Zone	Hazards description	Hazards characterization	Probability, %	Consequences		Risk Assessment Integrated
					Kind of Impact	Severity	
7 (6)	Southwestern slope of the 1-st Tisza River floodplain terrace	Erosion, technogenic flooding, etc.	Slope degradation, destroying	20	Economic impact	4	High
8 (7)	Western part of the Tisa River 1-st and 2nd floodplain terraces slopes	Erosion (tectonic dependent), technogenic flooding, etc.	Slope degradation, destroying, ravine formation	20	Economic impact	4	High
9	1-st and 2-nd Tisza River floodplain terrace southeastern slope	Erosion, paleolandslides, flooding, etc.	Slope degradation, destroying	15	Economic impact	3	Medium
11 ()	Mahura mount slope (eastern part)	Erosion, paleolandslides, etc.	Slope degradation, destroying	15	Economic impact	3	Medium
13 (8)	Mahura mount slope (western part)	Erosion, periodical, technogenic flooding	Slope degradation, destroying	10	Economic impact	2	Low

SEVERITY	CONSEQUENCES			PROBABILITY, %				
	People	Assets	Environment	< 1	1-10	11 - 49	50 - 90	> 90
1	Slight injury or health effect	Slight damage	Slight effect					
2	Minor injury or health effect	Minor damage	Major effect					
3	Major injury or health effect	Moderate damage	Moderate effect					
4	PTD or up to 3 fatalities	Major damage	Major effect					
5	More than 3 fatalities	Massive damage	Massive effect					

Risk Map of Natural and Natural-Antropogenic Hazards for Sopotvyno

Risk of natural and natural-antropogenic hazards (1-3):

1 – karst processes:

catastrophic (a), high (б), medium (в), low (г);

2 – slope erosion: high (a), medium (б), low (в);

3 – seasonal and flash floods:

high (a), medium (b), low (c);

4 – lakes and waterlogged lands of different genesis (natural and technogenic / antropogenic);

5 – rivers and streams;

6 – horizontals (though 5 m) and hypsometric data;

7 – sinkholes, collapses and weakened zones outlines;

8 – streets with buildings, roads, highway H09 (a), railway (b);

9 – Sopotvyno contour (a) and the state border zone (b);

10 – contours of mines (approximative);

11 – contours of mines (according to detailed engineering schemes, combined);

12 – main drainage galleries.

Risk Map of Natural and Natural-Antropogenic Hazards for Solotvyno (with critical infrastructure objects)

Risk of natural and natural-antropogenic hazards (1-3): 1 – karst processes: catastrophic (a), high (b), medium (c), low (d); 2 – slope erosion: high (a), medium (b), low (c); 3 – seasonal and flash floods: high (a), medium (b), low (c). Critical infrastructure objects (4-7): 4 – gas supply (gas distribution station & pipeline); 5 – power supply (110/35/6 kV power substation, 110 kV (a) and 6 kV (b) overhead power lines, 6 kV (c) cable power lines, low voltage power lines (d), electrical substation (e)); 6 – water supply (underground water supply, water well, pumping station); 7 – sewage treatment facilities (a) landfill (b). Sites of special permission land use (8-9): 8 – LLC “SPA Speleocenter Solotvyno”, valid (a), design (b); 9 – joint-stock company JSC “UkrGasVydobuvannya”, valid. Other keys: 10 – archaeological site of local importance (Chitattia settlement); 11 – lakes and waterlogged lands of different genesis (natural and technogenic / antropogenic); 12 – rivers and streams; 13 – horizontals (though 5 m) and hypsometric data; 14 – sink-holes, collapses and weakened zones outlines; 15 – streets with buildings, roads, highway H09 (a), railway (b); 16 – Solotvyno contour (a) and the state border zone (b); 17 – contours of mines (approximative); 18 – contours of mines (according to detailed engineering schemes, combined); 19 – main drainage galleries.

Sendai Framework exhorts us to reduce risk by

- *avoiding* decisions that create risk,
- *reducing* existing risk,
- *building* resilience.

ImProiret

!!! уникнення / обмеження діяльності з дестабілізації об'єктів критичної інфраструктури, зокрема, розташованих на схилах

Найвищі ризики карстово-суфозійних процесів існують в зонах 1, 2, 3

Виконати роботи з ліквідації аварійних споруд на території родовища

- обмежити перебування людей в цих зонах
- детально вивчити підземний простір по периферії зони 1 геофізичними методами та уточнити вірогідність провалоутворення

Упорядкування роботи дренажної штольневої системи та каналізації

Вирішення проблеми з освоєнням території дамби та покинутого об'єкту військової інфраструктури

Residential complexes that violate the surface of the dam and contribute to the development of erosion processes

Прийняттю обґрунтованих рішень сприятиме:

Створення постійнодіючої системи моніторингу

1. поверхневих,
2. підземних вод,
3. земної поверхні (зокрема для об'єктів критичної інфраструктури та будівель в зоні потенційного ризику)

Створення комплексної інженерно-геологічної моделі карстонебезпечної території для

- прогнозування процесів карстоутворення
- визначення вразливих зон
- встановлення меж зон неприпустимих ризиків
- обрахування / обґрунтування прийняття рішень

Final conference

ImProDiReT

*Improving Disaster
risk*

*Reduction in
Transcarpathian
region*

Solotvyno Case

*IGS NASU Results presented by
Stella Shekhunova*

Nyzne Solotvyno, 2020 – 01 – 29